

Active Device for Power Quality Enhancement of Electrified Transportation

H SURYA PRABHA, S MD RAFI, H HARITHA
ASSISTANT PROFESSOR^{1,2,3}

suryaprabha345@gmail.com, raficilen@gmail.com, harithah@svitatp.ac.in

Department of EEE, Sri Venkateswara Institute of Technology,
N.H 44, Hampapuram, Rapthadu, Anantapuramu, Andhra Pradesh 515722

Abstract: To improve power quality in single-phase systems with important loads, a transformerless hybrid series active filter (THSeAF) is suggested. This study aims to improve the link between electric vehicle loads and the grid, which in turn helps with energy management and power quality concerns associated to electric transportation. The goal of the control approach is to rectify the power factor of non-linear loads and prevent current harmonic distortions from flowing into the utility. The arrangement is excellent for industrial application because it protects sensitive loads from voltage fluctuations, sags, and surges caused by the power supply. This polyvalent hybrid architecture has the potential to either absorb or inject the auxiliary power back into the grid, enabling harmonic isolation and correction of voltage aberrations. In addition to practical research, the study delves into the impact of delays and gains on the stability of real-time controllers. The efficacy of the proposed topology was shown by the calculations and experimental findings that were carried out on a 2kVA laboratory prototype. Hybrid series active filter, electric car, power quality, real-time control, and current harmonics are index terms.

INTRODUCTION

The widespread use of electric vehicle battery charging stations has had negative effects on power distribution system harmonic voltage levels [3], and the predicted Smart Grids linked with these stations have caused serious concerns about the power system's quality in all respects. However, while designing new grids, it is important to account for the increasing harmonics caused by nonlinear loads, such as electric vehicle propulsion battery chargers [4, 5]. These loads do damage to the power system and plant equipment. Just as the higher rms and peak-value of the distorted current waveforms cause electrical equipment to fail, they also increase heating and losses. This issue has been appropriately resolved since it significantly decreases the efficiency of the system [6,7].

Additionally, dynamic voltage restoration function is recommended for protecting the point of common coupling (PCC) against voltage distortions. One way to address this problem is to cut down on power

electronics-related pollution right where it starts. A general solution is to be investigated despite many efforts at a case study particular one. Two distinct active power devices are available to address the above power quality concerns. The first group consists of hybrid type one filters and other series active filters. They were created with the goal of removing current harmonics caused by non-linear loads from the power grid. When compared to active filters of the shunt type, series-active filters produce fewer dispersed signals [8, 9]. In comparison to shunt types, series active filters have the benefit of poorer compensator vs load optimisation ratings [10]. But their industrial implementation was hindered by the insufficiency of an appropriate distribution system and the complexity of the isolation series transformer's setup. Addressing voltage concerns on sensitive loads was the motivation for developing the second category. Often referred to as Dynamic Voltage Restorers (DVRs), they share a layout with Series Active Filters. The control concept distinguishes these two groups. This variation is based on the function they provide inside the system. To solve all of these problems with only one combination, the hybrid series active filter (HSeAF) was suggested. In theory, they can eliminate voltage distortions at the PCC, rectify power factors, and compensate current harmonics [11,12]. It is a suitable contender for power quality investments due to these correct linkages. The three-phase series active filters have a lot of literature supporting them [13, 14], but the single-phase uses of these filters have received less attention. To remove current harmonics caused by a non-linear load from the grid-side connection, this study proposes a single-phase transformerless HSeAF [15]. It might readily take the place of the shunt active filter because to its smaller rating of up to 10% [16]. Additionally, it has the potential to reestablish a sinusoidal voltage at the common coupling load point. The suggested setup has the potential benefit of effectively compensating non-linear harmonic voltage and current generating loads. When it comes to distributed generating systems that heavily use renewable energy sources, the THSeAF is a viable alternative to traditional power transferring converters since it allows for independent control and operation of each phase [17]. Eliminating the expensive isolation transformer and promoting industrial use for filtering reasons, this study demonstrates that a three-phase converter may be separated into single-phase H-bridge converters. The system has shown to be quite effective in completing the asked-for compensatory chores for rectification.

of voltage restoration at the load terminal, correction of power factor, and distortions of current and voltage [18].

Here is the structure of the article: In the part that follows, the system architecture is introduced. The suggested configuration's operating concept is then described. The control algorithm used in this study is modelled and analysed in the third part. A short explanation of the dc voltage control and its implications is provided, followed by a detailed description of the voltage and current harmonic detection approach. A number of situations are simulated in order to assess the setup and the method

of control. It is possible to verify simulations by demonstrating experimental data obtained in a controlled environment. Additional mathematical advancements are shown in the appendix and conclusion, which summarise the article.

2. The Structure of the System Part A: Setting Up the System

Figure 1 shows the transformerless hybrid series active filter, which consists of an H-bridge converter linked in series between the power supply and the load. A shunt passive capacitor guarantees that current harmonics have a low impedance route. When the voltage drops, you may inject power from a DC auxiliary source. In reference [19], the DC link energy storage system is details. With this setup, you may get a rated power of 2200VA. The controller is implemented on a dSPACE/dsp1103 to guarantee a quick transient response with acceptable stability margins across a broad variety of operations. Table I lists the system parameters. A 120 Vrms variable source is coupled to a 998 VA linear load and a 1.1 kVA non-linear load, both of which have a power factor of 0.46. For the injection of the compensating

TABLE II

SINGLE-PHASE COMPARISON OF THE THSeAF TO PRIOR HSeAFs

voltage, the THSeAF is linked in series. A secondary DC-link energy storage device is mounted on the compensator's DC side. Practical implementation likewise makes use of similar parameters.

TABLE I CONFIGURATION PARAMETER

Symbol	Definition ^S	Value
V_s	Line phase-to-neutral voltage	120Vrms
f	System frequency	60Hz
$R_{non-linear load}$	Load resistance	11.5Ω
$L_{non-linear load}$	Load inductance	20mH
P_L	Linear load power	1kVA
PF	Linear load power factor	46%
L_f	Switching ripple filter inductance	5mH
C_f	Switching ripple filter capacitance	2μF
T_s	dSPACE Synchronous sampling time	40μs
f_{PWM}	PWM frequency	5kHz
G	Control gain for current harmonics	8Ω
V_{DCref}^*	VSIDC bus voltage of the THSeAF	70V
PI	Proportional gain(K), Integral gain(K)	0.025(4*)

Definition	Proposed THSeAF	[21]	[22]	[12]
Injection Transformer	Non	2 per phase	1 per phase	1 per phase
# of semiconductor devices	4	8	4	4
# of DC link storage elements	1+Aux Pow.	1	2	1+Aux Pow.
A Frating to the load power	10-30%	10-30%	10-30%	10-30%
Size and weight, regarding the transformer, power switches, drive circuit, heatsinks, etc.	The Lowest	High	Good	Good
Industrial production costs	The Lowest	High	Low	Low
Power losses, including switching, conducting, and fixed losses	Low	Better	Low	Low
Reliability regarding independent operation capability	Good	Low	Good	Good
Harmonic correction of Current source load	Good	Good	Good	Low
Voltage Harmonic correction at load terminals	Good	Better	Good	Good
Power factor correction	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Power injection to the grid	Yes	No	No	Yes

TABLE III
LABORATORY MEASURED VALUE AND POWER FLOW ANALYSIS

Measures	Load		Grid Utility (Source)	
	Voltage (V), V_L	Current (A), I_L	Voltage (V), V_s	Current (A), I_s
THD(%)	4.6	14.2	2.7	2.4
Fund.(rms)	119.9	16.7	121.2	12.8
Active power, P(W)	1499.7		1544.4	
Reactive power, Q(var)	1284.5		10.6	
Power, S(VA)	1998.6		1545.2	
Power Factor, PF	0.75		0.99	
Compensator, THSeAF	$S_{Comp} = +44W - j1274var$			

The current is kept at 130 Vdc. The compensator's job is to manage the magnitude of the load voltage, compensate for current harmonics, and fix the power factor when the grid experiences voltage distortion. Figure 11 shows the THSeAF simulation results, which show an improvement in the source current THD. Load terminal voltage VLTHD 4.3% and source voltage THDVS is 25%. Grid-perturbation reduces the THD to less than 4% and regular operation brings the grid-distorted current harmonics down to less than 1%. While

To clean the current of harmonic components, these regulated sources require the source current to be in phase with the source voltage. The series compensator may get the power factor up to one by adjusting the load voltage. In addition, the power flow between two PCCs might be controlled by the series compensator.

The findings of the laboratory experiments support the hypothesis predicted in Figure 10. The settings maintain the power factor and the grid

To regulate the current harmonics, a gain of 8 Ω , which is equal to 1.9 p.u., was used. The ability of operation with low DC voltage is one of the major

The current disturbance on the grid voltage cannot be controlled by THSeAF. By using a controlled voltage across the terminals of loads with a sensitive loads. The grid utility is further exposed to voltage magnitude volatility in the worst case scenario. In order to keep the load PCC voltage controlled at the right level, the compensator should additionally inject active power. The auxiliary source maintains the magnitude of the loadside voltage controlled by supplying the difference of power during voltage sags and swells. Presenting the source utility and load PCC's harmonic content and total harmonic distortion (THD) factor reveals significant gains in THD despite the load's contamination of the current waveforms. Additionally, when the grid's voltage is perturbed, the compensator in a hybrid system controls and sustains the voltage of a harmonic-free load.

SUMMARY

This study presents the results of developing and testing a Transformerless-HSeAF with the aim of improving power quality. In order to seamlessly connect electric vehicles' battery chargers to the grid, the study emphasised that future SmartGrids should consider tangible steps due to the ever-increasing non-linear loads and the growing demand from consumers for a stable supply. The suggested design has the potential to enhance the power quality of the system in a more general fashion by correcting a broad range of harmonic currents, which is the primary uniqueness of the approach. Regardless, the THSeAF controls and enhances the PCC voltage. The topology may actively contribute to the system's power flow when coupled with a renewable auxiliary source. To provide a steady supply for crucial loads, this vital capability is necessary. It makes sure there is unity power factor and cleans the power system by acting as a high harmonic impedance. An examination was conducted into the theoretical modelling of the suggested arrangement. We simulated and experimentally verified the suggested transformerless arrangement. By maintaining a steady and distortion-free supply at the load terminals, it was shown that this active compensator reacts appropriately to supply voltage changes. In addition, it enhances the grid's power quality without the usual large and expensive series transformer, and it removes source harmonic currents.

Section I: Recognisance
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